

“Formulation and Evaluation of Poly herbal cookies for diabetic patients using Physiochemical properties ”

Harsh shah ¹, Krishna Patil ², Jay parkhe³, Gopeshwar tripathi ⁴, Dr.Rakesh Kumar gawaly ⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Affiliation: Oriental College of Pharmacy, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh

ABSTRACT

Most of the people consume cookies during their breakfast, snacks and leisure time to regulate their hunger and get some energy, in market there are varieties of cookies which are available, and the main components are refined flour, sugar and butter. Hence, are generally avoided by obese and diabetic patients as they lead to high sugar level in blood. Therefore, in this recent investigation, we have formulated Polyherbal cookies using oats, wheat flour and different Ayurveda herb. Diverse varieties were formulated using different plant to find out the best composition for cookies on the basis of palatability. After selection, cookies were formulated for the physiochemical, sensory and their nutritional analysis. Sensory analysis was evaluated based on organoleptic characteristics: color, taste, aroma and overall acceptability on the basis of 9-paledonic scale. Physiochemical evaluation including: total ash value, total moisture content total water and alcoholic extraction, total moisture content. On the basis of its nutritional value comparison, it was found that the protein content is higher in our formulation than the other marketed preparation.

KEYWORDS

Polyherbal Cookies
Antidiabetic Cookies
Diabetes Mellitus
Functional Foods
Nutraceuticals
Physicochemical Evaluation
Sensory Analysis
Tecoma stans
Withania somnifera
Avena sativa
Herbal Formulation
Oat β-glucan
Nutritional Analysis
Phytochemical Screening
Herbal Drug Delivery System
Diabetic Nutrition
Ayurvedic Herbs
Protein-Rich Cookies
Low Glycemic Food
Herbal Functional Bakery Products

1. INTRODUCTION

Plants have provided a source of inspiration for novel drug compounds, as plant derived medicines have made large contributions of human health and well-being. Traditional medicine using plant extract continues to provide health coverage for over 80% of the world's population, especially in the developing world. Plants are used medicinally in different countries and are a source of many potent and powerful drugs.

Medicinal plants provide good remedies for human diseases and play a vital role in our day-to-day life. Indian systems of medicines are all based on the knowledge of drugs from plants. Higher plants, as sources of medicinal compounds, have continued to play a dominant role in the maintenance of human health since ancient time. Over 50% of all modern clinical drugs are natural product origin and natural products play an important role in drug development programs in the pharmaceutical industry. In India people have been used plants and natural products for the treatment of various diseases from ancient time. In the last two decades of the century the scientists are sincerely trying to evaluate many plant drugs used in traditional system of medicine.

[1]

Diabetes- common, non-communicable metabolic disorder mostly occurring in young ones and are associated with other diseases like kidney disease, cardiovascular diseases etc. It occurs when pancreas does not produce insulin or is not properly consumed by body. According to the WHO survey report globally, it is estimated that 422 million adults were suffering in 2014 and rate of increment is about from 4.7% to 8.5%. Diabetes mellitus, a chronic metabolic disease condition enounces by the elevated glucose level in blood (Hyperglycemia), hyperlipidemia, negative nitrogen balance, glycosuria and sometimes ketonemia. Basically, it is grouped in three main types: Type-1 diabetes mellitus / Insulin dependent diabetes mellitus/ Juvenile onset diabetes mellitus, which are mostly caused by the T-cell mediated autoimmune devastation of islets of insulin secretion Beta cells. Type-2diabetes mellitus /Non-Insulin Dependent diabetes mellitus occurs due to the moderate reduction in β cell mass or the low circulation of insulin due to the interaction of genetic or metabolic factor. Nearly 90% of diabetes patients are suffering from type-2 diabetes. And Type-3 occurred during pregnancy when insulin is not produced properly or the cells become resist to insulin.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 A Complete Review on *Avenasativa*

Kinthali Usha Rani et al, (2021),

The review of all clinical results study *Avena sativa* a potential candidate as nutraceutical & pharmaceutical agent. The advantages seen within clinical studies, but it must be well tried in larger studies for far exploration within therapeutic aspect would be helpful.

2.2 Evaluation of the Cookies Formulated with *Costus igneus* Plant Material for Antidiabetic Activity

A Rajani Chowdary et al, (2020),

The present research work aimed to formulate a nutritionally rich cookie with *Costus igneus* leaf extract and to determine the effect of cookie consumption on decreasing blood glucose level in type 2 Diabetic patient.

2.3 Therapeutic Properties and Applications of *Tecoma stans* Linn.

Abisha Vince Jeo V.S et al, (2020),

In the recent study, the researcher gave the evidence that it contains chemical constituents like alkaloids, amino acids, phytosterols, monoterpenes, triterpenes, glycosides and phenols, tannins, saponin & flavonoids. The present review comprises the pharmacological, phytochemical & therapeutic potential of *Tecoma stans*.

2.4 Formulation of Polyherbal Antidiabetic Cookies

Kajal Pathak et al, (2018),

The cookies are generally avoided by obese and diabetic patients as they cause high sugar level in blood. So, objective of present research was to formulate polyherbal Cookies with the help of oats, wheat flour & different Ayurvedic Herbs.

2.5 Phytopharmacology of Ashwagandha as an Anti-Diabetic Herb

Vikas Kumar et al, (2017),

The study aimed to focus on Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) extract & several pharmaceutical formulations containing them are currently often used as tonics useful for prevention and cure of mental health problems including sleep disturbances, accompanying chronic diseases. The *W. Somnifera* could be used for treatment of diabetes associated with metabolic disturbances.

4. DRUG PROFILE

Oats (*Avena sativa*) belongs to family Poaceae. It has soluble fibre known as beta glucan is polysaccharides which containing glucose residue binds with 1, 3 and 1, 4 bonds. Products that have β glucan have been used from thousands of years for human health, but β glucans has been recently scrutinized as active ingredient. Since then, they have been studied extensively for immune stimulation effects and developed for the treatment of various diseases including cancer, infectious diseases. Oat β glucan have been used for several clinical trials to reduce glucose. Studies showed that oat β glucan lowered postprandial glycemia. The effect of β glucans to reduce blood glucose could be mediated possibly by delaying stomach emptying so that dietary glucose is absorbed more gradually. After ingestion of oats (bran flour or crisp), the blood glucose level was lower at 15, 30 and 45 min but higher at 90 min after 12.5g glucose loading. Thus, the peak level is much smoothed and the shape of the plasma glucose response curve is flatter. These changes reduce the feeling of hunger caused by rapid decrease in blood glucose. Thus, β glucan may reduce appetite and reduce food intake. ^[4]

Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) belong to family Solanaceae. Ashwagandha root is mainly containing steroids and alkaloids that have rejuvenative herb that is used to treat mental health problem associated with other disease. It controls the lipid profile; cholesterol level and blood glucose level as compare to oral hypoglycemic agent. The flavonoids and antioxidant which is present in root of Ashwagandha is responsible for its antidiabetic property through improve the liver and kidney function and balanced albumin and globulin ratio that play a vital role to treat diabetes. ^[5]

Tecoma stans is commonly planted as an ornamental in warmer climates throughout the world because of its showy yellow flowers and pinnate foliage. *Tecoma stans* is an important medicinal plant. The major bioactive compounds like alkaloids, phenols, terpenoids, glycosides, flavonoids, saponins had been isolated from this plant. The leaves, bark and roots contain biologically active chemicals, and extracts from those tissues are in use as traditional folk medicines. The presence of phytoconstituents like phytosterol, triterpene, glycosides, phenols, flavonoids, saponins, and tannins either individually or combined together may exhibit the synergistic effect towards healing of wounds. ^[6]

Figure 1. *Tecoma stans* leaves

Figure 2. *Tecoma stans* bark

4.1 Scientific name: *Tecoma stans* (L.) Kunth.

Taxonomy:

Kingdom	Plantae - plantes, Planta, Vegetal, plants
Plantae	
Subkingdom	Viridaeplantae - green plants
Infrakingdom	Streptophyta - land plants
Division	Tracheophyta - vascular plants, tracheophytes
Subdivision	Spermatophytina - spermatophytes, seed plants, phanerogams
Infradivision	Angiospermae - flowering plants, angiosperms, plantas com flor, angiosperma, plantes à fleurs, angiospermes, plantes à fruits
Class	Magnoliopsida
Superorder	Asteranae
Order	Lamiales
Family	Bignoniaceae - bignonias
Genus	<i>Tecoma</i> Juss. - trumpetbush
Species	<i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.) Juss. ex Kunth - yellow elder, yellow trumpet-flower, trumpet bush, trumpet flower.

Description

Tecoma stans is a promising species in the trumpet vine family, Bignoniaceae. The common names are yellow trumpet bush, yellow bells, yellow elder and Esperanza. It is a flowering perennial shrub or small tree, 5-7.6 m in height. Bark is pale brown to grey and roughens with age. Leaves are opposite, compound and imparipinnate with 2 to 5 pairs of leaflets and a larger single terminal leaflet.

Another study shows a dramatic invitro anticancer activity of ethanolic leaf extract of *Tecoma stans* on human breast cancer cell line (MCF-7) at increasing concentrations with Inhibitory concentration 64.5µg/ml. [18-19]

4.2. Scientific Name: *Withania somnifera* (WS)

Taxonomy:

Kingdom	Plantae, Plants
Subkingdom	Tracheobionta, Vascular plants
Super division	Spermatophyta, Seeds plants
Division	Angiosperma
Class	Dicotyledons
Order	Tubiflorae
Family	Solanaceae
Genus	<i>Withania</i>
Specie	<i>Somnifera dunal</i>

Figure 3. *Withania somnifera*

Description

Also known as ashwagandha, Indian ginseng, and winter cherry, it has been an important herb in the Ayurvedic and indigenous medical systems for over 3000 years. The roots of the plant are categorised as rasayanas, which are reputed to promote health and longevity by augmenting defence against disease, arresting the ageing process, revitalising the body in debilitated conditions, increasing the capability of the individual to resist adverse environmental factors and by creating a sense of mental wellbeing.

observed. In the case of clinical trials on diabetes, despite not showing an effect on blood sugar levels, interesting results were achieved in improving the lipidemic profile, body weight, and blood pressure, showed an improvement in the lipidemic profile and patient assessment with the DDS17 scale assessing patients' distress scale. The administration of a standardized Ashwagandha extract under the name SENSORIL improved antioxidant parameters and the lipidemic profile and demonstrated the tolerability and safety of the raw material. In site of its tolerability and safety, demonstrated an effect on lipidemic profile and a change in the reflection index. ^[21-22]

4.3. Scientific Name:A vena sativa L

Kingdom	Plantae
Super division	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Liliopsida
Order	Cyperales
Family	Poaceae
Genus	Avena
Species	A. Sativa
Common Names	Oat, Cultivated Oat, Oats, Side Oat, Tree Oat, Red Oat

Figure 4. Avena sativa L

6. MATERIALS AND METHODS

6.1. Materials

Table No 1. List of ingredients used

Nameofingredients	Sources
Tecoma stans	Local area,
Ashwagandh a	Local area,
Tulsi	Local area,
Oats	Local market,
Milk	Local market,
Black gram flour	Local market,
Flavoring Agents	Local market,
Butter	Local market,
Salt	Local market,
Baking soda	Local market,
Baking powder	Local market,
Artificial sugar	Local market,
Wheat flour	Local market

Table No 2. list of equipments used

Nameof Equipment	Make/Mode
Digital Weighing Balance	MAB220, WENSAR
Soxhlet Apparatus	LTSW-5, LAB TECH
Hot Air Oven	S Clean-135947175, S Clean
Desiccator	JII-1504, A SKY INSTRUMENT

Collection of Sample

Fresh aerial parts of Tecoma stans (leaves), Ashwagandha (bark), and Tulsi (leaves) were collected from local areas of Chandrapur city. The collected plants were washed properly and sun dried. The dried plant was ground into coarse powder material and in sunlight container till future. Milk, Flavoring agent (vanilla and cocoa), salt, baking powder, baking soda, butter, were purchased from localmarket of Chandrapur and Artificial sugar (Diabliss sugar) was procured from its online store.

[25]

6.2. Methods

Preparation of Cookies

Different compositions of cookies were formulated using different ratios of Oats, wheat flour, roasted black-gram flour, Tecoma stans leaves powder, Ashwagandha powder, Tulsi powder, Milk, Flavoring agent (vanilla and cocoa), salt, baking powder, baking soda, butter, artificial sugar (sugar free Natura), and based on the palatability and visual appealing final product were selected for sensory evaluation and nutritional value analysis.

Figure 5. Preparation of cookie

Preliminary batches for polyherbal cookies

Table No 3. Preliminary batches for polyherbal cookies

Content	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Tecoma stans	15 gm.	13 gm. 8	15 gm.	12 gm.	20 gm. 5
As hwagandh a	10 gm. 5	gm.	12 gm. 3	10 gm. 8	gm.
Tulsi	gm. 40	9 gm. 40	gm. 40	gm. 40	5 gm. 40
Oats	gm. 10				
Milk	ml. 40				
	gm. 1				
Black gram flour	ml.	ml.	ml.	ml.	ml.
Flavoring Agents	15 ml.				
Butter	1 gm.				
Salt	1 gm.				
Baking soda	1 gm.				
Baking powder	1.5 gm				
Artificial sugar	10 gm.				
Wheat flour	100 gm.				

7. EVALUATION PARAMETERS

7.1. Phytochemical Evaluation of Powdered Flower Extract of *Tecoma stans*

The powdered flower sample of *Tecoma stans* was taken and phytochemical screening was done to check the phytoconstituents present using standard reagents.

a) Carbohydrates

Molisch's test:

About 2ml of powdered flower extract was mixed with 0.2 ml of alcoholic solution of α -naphthol 10% in addition to 2 ml of sulphuric acid, a bluish violet zone is formed this indicates the presence of carbohydrates and /or glycosides.

b) Alkaloids

About 0.2 g of the powdered flower extracts was warmed with 2% H₂SO₄ for two minutes. It was filtered and few drops of Dragendorff's reagent were added. Orange red precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

c) Tannins

Small quantity of powdered flower extract was mixed with water and heated on water bath. The mixture was filtered and ferric chloride was added to the filtrate. A dark green solution indicates the presence of tannins.

d) Glycosides

The powdered flower extract was hydrolysed with HCl solution and neutralized with NaOH solution. A few drops of Fehling's solution A and B were added. Red precipitate indicates the presence of glycosides.

e) Saponins

About 0.2 g of the powdered flower extract was shaken with 5ml of distilled water and then heated to boil. Frothing (Appearance of creamy mass of small bubbles) shows the presence of saponins.

f) Flavonoids

Powdered flower extract of about 0.2 g was dissolved in diluted NaOH and HCl was added. A yellow solution that turns colourless, indicates the presence of flavonoids.

7.2. Physiochemical Properties of Cookies

a) Moisture content:

Moisture content was determined by the method prescribed in the chemical Analysis of the food. As stated in the procedure, sample of the cookies were weighed precisely in a moisture dish and were kept in hot air oven for about 2 hours at 105°C and then it was cooled in desiccators and again weighed. The process of heating was repeated for 30 min. and then again cooled and weighed. The procedure was done until the variance between two successive

weighing became less than that of 0.001 gm. Moisture content in the test sample was calculated

which was based on the equation given below:

$$\text{Moisture \% by weight} = \frac{100(w_1 - w_2)}{w_1 - w}$$

Where,

W₁ = Weight of moisture dish with sample before drying;

W₂ = Weight of moisture dish with sample after drying;

W = Weight of moisture dish.

b) Ash value:

Total ash content of the prepared cookies was determined by the following procedure. According to the given procedure 1 gm of cookie sample was taken in a tarred crucible and it was burnt on the Bunsen burner until all the carbon was burnt. Then Sample was let to be cooled, weighed and then again the procedure was repeated until the weight became constant. After that the total Ash value were calculated based on the equation given below:

$$\text{Total ash content (\% by weight)} = \frac{100(w_1 - w_2)}{w_1 - w}$$

Where,

W₂ = Weight of empty dish;

W = Weight of sample taken;

W₁ = Weight of crucible with sample after complete burn.

c) Total alcoholic and water extractive values:

For the analysis of total alcohol/Water extractive value, 5 gm of cookies powder sample were taken in 250 ml of volumetric flasks in which 90% ethyl alcohol or Distilled water were added and was kept aside for 24 hours. After the completion of 24-hour samples were filtered and

were taken in porcelain dishes. All the samples of alcoholic and water extracts were heated at the temperature of 100°C for evaporation, following samples were cooled down and advance calculations were done by the following method.

Calculation: 5 gm of sample gives 4x of alcohol extract so 100 gm of sample gives = $80 \times x/4$

Where, x=Sample after drying. [2]

7.3. Nutritional analysis

a) Protein estimation:

Protein estimation was done by prescribed procedure in the given DGHS Manual. According to this method 200-300 mg of cookies powder were taken in 4 test tubes and then 3 gm of catalyst (K₂SO₄+CuSO₄) was added in it. 10 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid H₂SO₄ was added to all tubes and then digested for 3-4 hrs. Later these samples were distilled with boric acid, potassium permanganate and 40% of Sodium hydroxide and then were titrated with acid. This titrant was neutralized with ammonia and by this % of protein was calculated by using following equation.

$$\text{Protein concentration} = \frac{\text{Amount of sample in } \mu\text{g} \times 1000}{V (\mu\text{l})}$$

b) Fat content:

According to the given procedure, 2 gm of the cookie sample was kept in Soxhlet apparatus with diethyl alcohol and petroleum ether in the ratio of 1:1 for 6 hours then ether was removed by the process of distillation and were dried in hot air oven at $110 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and later on was cooled in a desiccator. Taken dried sample was weighed again. The left Residue was washed with 2 to 3 ml of diethyl ether and the same process was repeated until the weight became constant.

$$\% \text{ of fat content} = (M1 - M2) \times 100 / \text{weight of the sample}$$

Where,

M1 = Weigh of Round bottom flask with fat;

M2 = Weigh of the Round bottom flask.

c) Carbohydrate estimation:

Carbohydrate estimation was done by the procedure given in DGHS Manual. For estimation of carbohydrate 2 gm of cookie sample powder was taken in a 200 ml of volumetric flask and then 50 ml of lead acetate was added. 6 ml of 0.5 N HCl was added and heated on hot water bath. After heating, the sample was cooled and neutralized with 6 ml of 0.5 N NaOH, lastly the sample volume was makeup upto 200 ml using distilled water, Invert sugar was determined before inversion by Lane and Eynon method.

According to this method 10 ml of mixed Fehling A and B solution was taken in the conical flask and titration was passed out with sample solution within 3 min without inversion by using 1% aqueous Methylene Blue as an indicator.

$$\text{Reducing sugar \% before inversion} = F \times 10 / C \times R$$

Where, C = concentration; R = Reading; F = Factor of Fehling solution

$$\text{Total invert sugar \% after inversion} = F \times 10 / C \times R$$

C = concentration; R = Reading; F = Factor of Fehling solution

Total carbohydrate = total invert sugar after inversion - invert sugar % before inversion x 0.95

d) Total Energy

Total energy was valued on the basis of carbohydrates, proteins and fats content of cookie sample.

$$\text{Energy (Kcal)} = \text{Fat} \times 4 + \text{Protein} \times 9 + \text{Carbohydrates} \times 4$$

e) Sensory Analysis

Sensory attributes such as flavor, aroma, taste, appearance and odor were evaluated by 9-point hedonic scale, total 64 people participated in this survey. Questionnaires and mouth rinsing water were conferred to taste panelist, through the session product was introduced and questions were explained to the volunteers. The obtained data were analyzed by Microsoft Excel on the basis of age group. ^[27]

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4: Chemical and physiochemical parameter

Sr. no	Chemical and physiochemical parameters	Results
1	Ash content	7.10%
2	Moisture content	6.91%
3	Alkaloid	Present
4	Alcohol extraction	6.58%
5	Water extraction	5.30%
6	Fat content	14.04%
7	Carbohydrate content	60.51%
8	Protein content	11.65
9	Total energy	414.9874 Kcal

By above mentioned Table 1 of results shown, those Cookies were spanning in nutritional values with controlled fat and carbohydrate and high rich in protein content which have made it acceptable among the health-conscious people, growing people and case of malnutrition. Comparative studies of different parameters of sensory evaluation exhibited that use of curry leaves as an active ingredient has given an appetizing and flavoring effect. Selected composition of cookies has made it acceptable around 90-96% that will give us a hope to convert this formulation into large scale production. In terms of physiochemical properties, nutrition value, sensory evaluation and comparison with other marketed product were in acceptable range.

8.1. Sensory Evaluation

Taste is a strategic parameter of sensory evaluation. The product might be captivating and having an eminent energy but sans of righteous taste it is likely to unaccepted. So, on the basis of sensory evaluation, it is found that due to use of Tecoma stans leaves its mean score was 90-95% among the age group of 18-40. Graph of taste has been depicted below (Figure No. 6).

Figure 6: Acceptance of taste

8.2. Flavour

Flavour is an integral part of taste that plays a vital role in the acceptance of any food material. Used flavour of Tecoma stans leaves and coco was found to be highly appreciable among all the volunteer of sensory evaluation because its smell act as an appetizer, because of that it means score on excel was found to be 90-95% (Figure No. 7).

Figure 7: Acceptance of flavor

8.3. Aroma and Color

Aroma or fragrance of foods are the indiscernible part of the acceptance and play a crucial role in mouth feel. Aroma is the first sign of consumer to choose any food for consumption as well as color of food product is a sign of acceptance that have a great impact on the choice of any product. Aroma and color show an elegant effect on the acceptance.

The outcome of results showed that strong combined Tecoma stans leaves, Ashwagandha and Tulsi

powder's aroma influenced the people greatly.

8.4. Overall Acceptance of Cookies

It is very important for food, snacks, and soft drinks that after taking the bite or sip it must give a palatable and flavourful effect on the tongue so it could be taken easily. The results of sensory evaluation on the basis of taste, flavour, crispiness and aroma were found to be appreciable with medicated effect.

8.5. Comparative Study of Nutritional Factor

Nutritional factor is the main aim of this study. After completion of all evaluation when it was compared with different brands of biscuits and it was found that it has less fat and carbohydrate which is highly beneficial for diabetic patients as well as high protein content due to use of black gram powder, this makes it protein rich which might be useful for growing and malnourished children (Figure No. 8).

Figure 8: Comparative studies with other marked product

9. CONCLUSION

Based on statistical data it was found that herbal cookies have high amount of protein, controlled amount of fat and carbohydrate in compared to other marketed product. Presence of Tecoma stans leaves and ashwagandha bark have given a new direction to convert home remedies into a marketed preparation which gives the highest acceptance in terms of flavor as well as the ingredients used in formulation has already proven significant role to control non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus and other health issue. So, it could be serviceable in the manufacturing of highly nutritious cookies with low cost and high efficiency.

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